

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING PHYSICS BASED ON INTEGRATION WITH SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

¹Kurbanov M., ²Kurbanov X.M., ²Mansurova M.Yu., ¹Sodiqova Sh.M.

¹ Professor of National University of Uzbekistan

²Tashkent State University of Transport, PhD, Associate Professor

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Abstract. *The given article presents the aim of improving the professional training of students of technical universities, the article considers the issues of teaching based on the integration of physics and specialized subjects. It also describes the features of the structure of the teaching methodology and the organization of physics classes when mastering specialized disciplines in engineering and technical universities.*

Keywords: *technician, engineer, integration, specialization, methodology, special course, standard, physics, education, talent, fundamental, professional training, research activity, component, criterion, content.*

It is important to suggest that at the present stage of development of higher technical education, the key place is occupied by deepening the scientific training of future technical specialists. The main role of the physics course as a theoretical basis for general and special sciences is a characteristic feature of the content of professional training of future engineers. However, the professional focus of teaching in the standard physics program of higher technical and engineering educational institutions is not reflected, that is, students do not see the connection between physics and general and special sciences and cannot apply physical laws and phenomena in subjects in their professional activities.

Let us consider the solution to the problem of creating and teaching special courses based on the integration of physics with the core subjects of the block of natural sciences and humanities in the curriculum in order to improve the professional training of students of technical and engineering universities.

Special courses on physics in technical and engineering universities represent educational activities in the block of natural sciences and humanities, which is part of the national-regional component of the State Educational Standard (SES).

These special courses allow combining both fundamental and special physical theories with technical theories, help to project physical phenomena and laws onto objects of professional activity (technological processes, processing and control methods, technical devices, etc.).

What is more important, we use the idea of a systems approach when developing a methodology for teaching special courses on physics in technical and engineering universities.

Definitely, an improved model of a unified education system in technical and engineering universities has been created, taking into account the features of the methodology for teaching special courses on physics, creative and technical talents of future specialists, development of skills and abilities, and formation of professional competencies (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Improved model of teaching courses in physics specialty for students of engineering and technical universities.

The methodology for teaching special courses on physics in technical universities is a set of interrelated elements that form a single whole: learning objectives, pedagogical interaction between a teacher and a student, turning a student into a subject of educational activity through a set of pedagogical influences (content, forms of organization, methods, means). The main objective of the teaching methodology is to teach students to apply basic physical phenomena and laws to various objects of professional activity, as well as to take into account the traditions of the development of the railway industry, social order and reflection of the personal potential of the

student, deep fundamental career guidance. Training of students of technical and engineering universities is aimed at meeting the needs of the individual and the needs of society. The content of special courses on physics includes fundamental knowledge (physical laws, concepts, scientific theories) and career guidance knowledge (professional application of physical laws, concepts, theories aimed at solving problems of the railway track), as well as the content of educational material, which includes elements of scientific and research activities. For example, methods of deformation and flaw detection of metal parts of rails and switch conductors in the system "Repair and Maintenance of Railway Track" provide detection based on the principles of flaw detection of rails by magnetic and ultrasonic methods. Thus, students learn about the classification of rails, the weight and dimensions of rails, rail materials, the purpose of rails and the requirements for them, which are the basis for the production of high-quality track products.

It is known to everyone; we call such a special course "Mechanical Properties of Solids". The content of such a special course includes situations when it is necessary to know in advance the strength of materials such as steel, invisible in technical devices and objects, how materials bend and behave under large deformations and under what conditions they begin to deform. Thus, teaching special courses on physics for students of technical and engineering universities is carried out at two different levels. Since one of the goals of teaching special courses on physics is to consolidate and expand fundamental knowledge on physics, the first level is considered invariant (basic), the leading principle of which is the principle of fundamental materiality and the existence of ordered interdisciplinarity. However, teaching special courses on physics for students of technical and engineering universities has its own goals: to create a scientific basis for the study of general and special subjects by students; the formation of activities suitable for the professional activity of an engineer; the formation of students' abilities for scientific and research activities, etc. Therefore, at the second variable (practical) level, it is aimed at applying physical laws and phenomena in objects of professional activity, when solving specific engineering problems. The content of the variable part of the special course on physics should be related to the content of the professional and special training of students. Therefore, at the second level, the didactic process should be carried out on the basis of the principle of an interdisciplinary approach and orientation of training towards the profession. The principle of professional orientation allows introducing material of professional significance into training based on the analysis of the content of general and special subjects. Career guidance material of special courses on physics should contribute to the:

- Satisfaction of didactic principles (scientifically understandable joint behavior, evidence, systematicity and consistency, interdisciplinary and inter-cycle connections, etc.);
- Rely on the content of the basic physics course, supplement it and create conditions for the successful application of the acquired skills in professional activities;
- Correspondence to the professional profile of students;
- Presentation of current technical issues, basic methods of measurement and analysis, the latest methods of processing materials based on physical theories;
- Formation of students' ability to scientific and research activities.

Certainly, employee for determining the career guidance content of special courses on physics for students of technical and engineering universities:

1) select objects and technological operations that the future specialist will have to work on (device, technological process, quality control methods, innovative methods of processing materials);

2) distinguishes between technological operations and production processes performed using physical phenomena and laws (magnetic control method, fluorescent control method, determination of coating thickness, electric spark processing of materials, etc.);

3) it is necessary to select professional material that clearly distinguishes physical laws (provides a clear idea of the use of a particular law or phenomenon), does not hide the material of the physics course, but is inextricably linked with physical theories. When developing the content of educational material for special courses on physics, it is advisable to use the following criteria, including the criteria proposed by the author, as well as individual criteria used in studying the physics course in technical and engineering higher educational institutions:

1. The criterion of interdisciplinary connections, i.e. the material being studied should be considered both in the general physics course and in special physics courses.

2. The criterion of content consistency. The sequence of content is considered as "relevance" to the elements of physical knowledge that students already have.

3. The criterion of limited inclusion of engineering and technical information. Engineering information should be introduced with particular caution, since in special physics courses this information should be presented in a simplified and schematic manner.

4. The criterion of preliminary provision of information. The input should be made in advance, taking into account its prospects compared to the average level of development of the industry. It is necessary to consider the physical basis for the operation of devices that have not yet become widespread or are just beginning to be introduced on modern railways. Such anticipation creates an educational basis and forms a guiding basis for actions not only for the period of study at the university, but also for a certain period of professional activity.

5. The criterion of the sequence of introducing content into the logic of professional activity. Incorporating the content of a special course into the logic of professional activity allows one to significantly increase interest in the material being studied and comprehensively update the existing physical knowledge.

6. The criterion for the completeness of the course content within the allotted time. The task is to establish the relationship between physical phenomena, laws and principles of operation of a particular device within a limited time frame and to find out what is more important from the point of view of future professional activity.

Additionally, the criterion for collective consideration of the physical basis of operation of tools and devices. When studying the physical foundations of technical devices, we encounter not one, but several laws or rules underlying them. Therefore, we need to look at the use of all physical laws, phenomena and their interrelations in order to create a full-fledged picture of how the device works. Such a structure of the content of special courses on physics allows one to update the entire set of physical knowledge obtained during the study of the main course on physics, which at the same time has professional significance.

It is not a secret that the principle of fundamental teaching and unity of professional focus is the leading idea underlying the methodology of special courses on physics for students of technical and engineering universities. This principle ensures a holistic connection between physical theories and technical processes. In this case, students' cognitive activity will be

connected with scientific and technical theories of industrial technologies and theoretical schemes of industrial equipment through fundamental physical theories. For example, the combination of physical theories with the rules of chemistry and materials science leads to the creation of scientific and technical theories of industrial technologies of electrical erosion, electric spark, laser processing, etc. Within the framework of the special course on physics "Physicochemical Methods of Processing", one can study the physical foundations of the above technologies. As an example of theoretical schemes in scientific theories of industrial technologies, the following are given: inductor schemes for magnetic-abrasive processing of parts; pulse generator scheme for electrical discharge processing of parts; ultrasonic generator scheme for ultrasonic processing of semiconductors; schemes of other units that form the basis of industrial devices and technologies can be given. Teaching methods and technologies are the ways of realizing the goals and content. Among them, the priority is given to the methods that form in engineering students the ability to apply knowledge of physics to objects related to the professional activity of an engineer, and the ability to carry out scientific research activities. Among them: gnostic methods (problem setting, partial research, research, etc.), methods of independent management of educational activities (literature, independent work on problems, etc.), control methods (laboratory, machine, self-control, etc.) directly depend on the forms, methods and content of training. When studying special courses on physics, it is advisable to use all forms of training (lectures, laboratory classes), including independent work. Lectures on special courses include theoretical material reflecting the content of a specific special course, including the fundamental physical foundations of processes and phenomena occurring in technology.

Besides that, laboratory training should be carried out on special equipment (spectrographs, models of spraying and coating application, X-ray equipment, electrical discharge equipment, etc.), which significantly expands the course of physics and directs it to future specialization. Independent work occupies a special place in specialized courses on physics. Within the framework of independent work, promising scientific and production areas of a specific engineering specialty, innovative processing methods, modern methods of monitoring track products are considered, which undoubtedly increases students' interest in science, contributes to the formation of skills in conducting research work. Methods and forms of organizing the educational process are implemented through didactic means of knowledge formation and professional activity. A set of tasks and information and computer support developed during the study and recommended for use in technical and engineering universities is an effective tool that allows you to go beyond the experiment and study physical processes and phenomena in a wider field of science. The set of tasks includes the following: tasks aimed at developing knowledge of lecture material of special sciences, tasks aimed at developing skills in solving real engineering problems, tasks for laboratory work aimed at developing skills in conducting experiments using professional subjects, independent and scientific research work, tasks for developing creative thinking. In higher technical and engineering educational institutions, it is desirable to include not one special course on physics, but a set of special courses of two levels: introductory and research. This allows students to move from the level II of mastering physical knowledge (active assimilation of the covered physical material) to levels III and IV (application of acquired knowledge in professional activities and development of students' abilities for scientific and research activities). The above-mentioned levels of knowledge acquisition V.P. Bospalko [4, pp. 123-135], and in higher school L.V. Maslennikova [5, pp. 85-105], use it when teaching physics

in technical and engineering universities. Thus, in the 2nd year, when preparing students for an engineering specialty, it is proposed to take special physics courses that introduce future engineers to the specialty and provide preliminary information on engineering problems and issues [2, pp. 35-48].

For example, the special course "Mechanical Failures in Mechanical Engineering" introduces students to the basics of mechanical damage common in track materials and engineering equipment. In the 3rd year, when students acquire certain knowledge, special research courses on physics, chemistry, mathematics, theoretical mechanics, materials science, and construction materials technology are included, which are studied in full. For example, the special course "Physical Foundations of Solid State Testing Methods" allows you to consider modern methods of non-destructive testing of track products [1, pp. 71-90]. We have developed an algorithm for recruiting special physics courses in technical and engineering universities:

1. Create a logical structure of special physics courses for students of engineering and technical universities, based on fundamental knowledge of physics and focused on modern scientific knowledge and the latest achievements in the field of railway transport.

2. Develop a system of principles and criteria for selecting the content of a special physics course for students of technical and engineering universities.

3. Creation of the content of a special course on physics based on these principles and a system of criteria.

4. Determination of teaching methods, forms and means of teaching special courses on physics.

5. Development of a set of tasks for various forms of educational activity (lectures, laboratory and independent work).

In order to test the effectiveness of the developed methodology for teaching special courses on physics, students in the experimental and control groups were offered a diagnostic test with three levels of tasks: the first was the level of mastery based on understanding fundamental physical laws, the second was knowledge in solving physical problems related to production facilities and technological processes, the level of ability to apply, and the third was the level of ability to apply knowledge obtained in special courses on physics in matters of scientific research. The results of the test are presented in the diagram (Fig. 2).

As can be seen from the diagram, the number of students who completed the tasks of each level is higher in the experimental groups than in the control groups [3, 235-248b.].

It is necessary to calculate the learning outcomes not only in physics, but also in special courses in other subjects. The proposed teaching outcomes show the influence of knowledge obtained in studying special courses on physics on the level of studying general and specialized subjects. The decisive criterion for the effectiveness of the methodology should be considered the completion of course and diploma qualification projects, as well as the formation of creative thinking in future technical and engineering specialists. The development of general professional ("Fundamentals of Railway Transport", "Engineering and Computer Graphics") and specialization ("Technology and Mechanization of Railway Construction", "Scientific Research and Design of Railways", "Organization and Planning of Railway Construction") comparison allows us to note that this is 16% higher than in the experimental and control groups.

Figure 2. Diagnostic test work of students in the experimental and control groups, results of completion (% completed).

Also, in the experimental groups, a large number of students successfully defend term papers and final qualification papers. It should be noted that the students of the experimental groups who entered the master's program showed creative initiative and independence in the implementation and defense of the master's dissertation, especially in the research part. The opinions of teachers conducting training in specialized subjects indicate that students of the experimental groups are able to apply knowledge of physics at railway facilities and have the skills and abilities to conduct scientific research.

Analyzing the results of the pedagogical experiment conducted in universities, it shows that students of technical and engineering universities studying according to the methodology we developed have a high level of fundamental knowledge on physics, skills in using this knowledge in solving professional problems and the ability to conduct scientific and research activities.

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